

COPING MECHANISM ON ACADEMIC BURNOUT REDUCTION

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Coping Mechanism on Academic Burnout Reduction

Leighna Blessy T. Robles,* Emerald Jane F. Ramos, Ellyza Joy F. Balmes, Jillian Justine R. Feniquito, Mark Leander V. Cheungkock, Kathleen D. U. San Juan
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Academic burnout is a pervasive issue among students, leading to exhaustion, disengagement, and negative impacts on mental health. This study investigates academic burnout and coping mechanisms among students. Data was collected from 337 students using standardized tools, including the Oldenburg Burnout Inventory for Students and the Brief-COPE questionnaire. The results indicate high levels of academic burnout, particularly in terms of exhaustion and disengagement. Additionally, students employ various coping mechanisms, with moderate engagement in problem-focused and emotion-focused strategies, and lesser use of avoidant coping. Furthermore, correlation analysis reveals significant relationships between academic burnout and coping mechanisms, highlighting the need for targeted interventions. Recommendations include providing resources and support for students experiencing burnout, promoting healthy coping mechanisms, and implementing stress management programs. Longitudinal studies are recommended to assess the long-term effects of coping strategies on academic burnout and well-being. Ultimately, addressing academic burnout and enhancing coping mechanisms are crucial for promoting student well-being and academic success.

Keywords: *coping mechanisms, academic, burnout, reduction*

Introduction

Academic burnout is one of the most challenging problems to deal with as it can lead to exhaustion, lack of motivation, anxiety, and disengagement. This burnout is often caused by heavy workloads and an inability to balance classroom expectations with personal needs. Students frequently experience academic burnout, which is characterized by disengagement from learning, poor academic performance, and emotional exhaustion (Thi & Duong et al., 2024).

According to Marôco et al. (2020), student burnout is defined as exhaustion due to school demands, a cynical attitude toward learning, and feelings of academic inefficacy. Additionally, research suggests that burnout can occur when students perceive a lack of meaningful opportunities in their environment, leading to feelings of exhaustion and disengagement (Wang et al., 2022).

Burnout refers to the feeling of consuming one's energy or experiencing exhaustion (WHO, 2019). With high academic demands, excessive workloads, and prolonged stress, students may feel emotional and physical exhaustion. As stress increases, students may lose interest or motivation in tasks. Furthermore, a study conducted by Deloitte as cited by Mind You (2022), revealed that 70% of Gen Zs and 63% of millennials in the Philippines are experiencing burnout due to the demands of their workload. What is more alarming is that this number is significantly higher than the global average of 45%. This means that the majority of students and workers in the Philippines have experienced or will experience burnout due to school/work-related stress. However, this national prevalence of burnout also translates to higher incidences of anxiety and stress, with 48% of millennials and 68% of Gen Z in the Philippines claiming to be anxious and stressed out most of the time, higher than the global average of 46% for Gen Z and 38% for millennials.

The executive branch of the Philippine government, known as the Department of Health (DOH Filipino: Kagawaran ng Kalusugan), is responsible for ensuring that all Filipinos have access to basic public health services and providing high-quality medical treatment. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2018), 17% of teenage Filipinos attempted suicide in the previous year, with 11.1% devising a thorough plan to end their lives. Mental health refers to a person's condition concerning their psychological and emotional well-being. The most common mental health problems among adolescents include anxiety disorders, depression and other mood disorders, and behavioral and cognitive disorders. Among students aged 13-15 years old, 12 out of 100 seriously attempted suicide. Within this age group, 11.5% of students had seriously considered attempting suicide in the past 12 months before the survey, and 17% had experienced suicidal thoughts. Among junior high school students, 11% had devised a thorough plan to end their lives, while 17% of Filipino teenagers experiencing academic burnout had attempted suicide at least once. This study aims to investigate the coping mechanisms that students employ to reduce academic burnout.

As mentioned in Republic Act No. 11036, an act establishing a national mental health policy for the purpose of enhancing the delivery of integrated mental health services, promoting and protecting the rights of persons utilizing psychiatric, neurologic, and psychosocial health services, appropriating funds therefor, and for other purposes. In order to promote students' well-being, this act may protect them from academic burnout and its harmful impact on their mental health. Academic burnout will be included in this act since it can cause depersonalization, depression, lack of motivation, and other adverse effects on students' mental health. Prior research has demonstrated that student burnout increases during adolescence and is linked to both depressive symptoms and school involvement (Fiorilli, 2017).

Thus, the goal of this study is to identify and investigate the connection between academic burnout and the coping mechanisms of

students for preventing academic burnout. This study also aims to reduce academic burnout by examining the various coping mechanisms used by students. Coping mechanisms are the ways students deal with stress, hurdles, and challenges. Examples of such activities include exercise, meditation, journaling, seeking assistance from others, and participating in hobbies. These activities can help decrease academic fatigue among students by engaging and inspiring them in their studies and school activities.

Research Questions

The study aims to explore various strategies or techniques that individuals, particularly students, can apply to reduce academic burnout. Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. How do respondents describe their academic burnout in terms of:
 - 1.1. Exhaustion
 - 1.2. Disengagement
2. How do respondents describe their coping mechanisms in terms of:
 - 2.1. Problem-Focused Coping
 - 2.2. Emotion-Focused Coping
 - 2.3. Avoidant Coping
3. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' level of academic burnout and their coping mechanisms?
4. What are the interventions that can be followed in order to address academic burnout for students?

Literature Review

Academic burnout, which is common among students worldwide, has been widely studied to determine predictors, impacts, and coping strategies. Oyoo and Mutua (2019) recognized social support, particularly from teachers, to be crucial in preventing academic burnout. Furthermore, Alami et al. (2020) identified a correlation between burnout and depression in high school learners, underlining the necessity for comprehensive treatments. Coping strategies, ranging from problem-solving to avoidant behaviors, play a significant role in burnout management, with gender and cultural implications noted. In addition, the association between burnout and coping methods emphasizes the necessity of adaptive responses to stresses, with tolerance of ambiguity appearing as a key element. Considering the significance of coping strategies in reducing academic burnout, this literature review focuses on several studies that examine coping mechanisms to lessen academic burnout in students.

The issue of academic burnout among high school students has garnered considerable attention in recent research. Oyoo and Mutua (2019) conducted a correlational study involving 714 form four students from public secondary schools in Homa-Bay County, Kenya. Based on the results, social support was a significant predictor of academic burnout, meaning that students with higher levels of social support had lower rates of burnout. Their study demonstrated the varying effects of social support on different aspects of academic burnout. They discovered that the reduction of emotional tiredness, cynicism, and general academic burnout was most successful when teacher support was provided. This resonates with the broader understanding of the influential role of teacher support in promoting students' well-being and academic performance.

However, though social support was generally beneficial in reducing academic burnout, they have also identified some possible disadvantages. Providing too much instrumental support—such as helping with homework—may make students more likely to experience burnout by putting more pressure on them to meet expectations.

Furthermore, the focus of their study on high school students contrasts with previous research involving university students from diverse countries. Variations in academic environments and stressors between these educational stages may influence the observed relationships. Addressing these differences could offer valuable insights into the operation of academic resilience across various educational contexts.

Alami et al. (2020) examined the prevalence of depression and burnout among high school students, highlighting the negative effects of school-related issues on the mental health of teenagers, to supplement these studies. The results of their study revealed that students experience high levels of emotional exhaustion, disengagement, and depersonalization, suggesting that burnout is a significant problem in secondary education settings. Furthermore, the results have shown that school-related issues play a major role in causing burnout in teenagers, with fear of failure or not meeting academic standards being one of the main reasons.

Expanding on the results of the previous studies, Dogan and Dogan (2023) carried out a systematic review with an emphasis on school burnout among secondary and high school students. The negative correlation between academic achievement and school burnout was made clear by their examination of thirty-eight studies, highlighting the roles of emotional exhaustion, academic pressure, and family involvement, which further emphasized the significance of understanding the complex interplay between motivational and cognitive factors in improving students' experiences of burnout and academic performance.

However, considering the results of the review, further research is required to explore the intermediate factors that play a role between burnout in middle and high school students and their academic achievement. Understanding the connection between school burnout and other motivational and cognitive factors within the school context, such as self-efficacy, is particularly intriguing. Given the varied

outcomes reported in studies regarding the nature of this relationship, investigating this is crucial.

Kucharzyk and Bednarek (2023) conducted a study to assess the level of school stress among high school students. They found that approximately 46.8% of secondary school students reported moderate levels of perceived stress. Despite variations in age, gender, and academic background, the overall prevalence of stress remained consistent among the student population.

In terms of coping strategies used by high school students to manage stress, a variety of approaches were identified, including problem-focused coping, emotion-focused coping, and avoidance coping. Results highlighted acceptance, self-focus, and positive coping as the most common strategies used by study participants. These strategies involve directly addressing stressors, managing emotions, and actively seeking solutions to reduce stress. In contrast, the use of avoidant coping strategies, such as substance use, is less common among students.

Furthermore, it was discovered that female adolescents tend to employ problem-solving and emotion-regulating coping strategies more often than males. Conversely, male adolescents are more inclined to utilize avoidant coping strategies, such as venting and self-blame (Sağar, 2022).

Al-Tell and Mansor (2019) conducted a study at government schools in Northern West Bank, Palestine, to examine stress management strategies among secondary school-aged students. They found that religion and planning were students' predominant coping methods. The cultural context influenced the choice of coping strategies, with religious practices being a prominent means of coping with stress.

High school students employ a variety of coping strategies to deal with school-related stress. Problem-focused coping strategies, emotion-focused coping strategies, and avoidant coping mechanisms are commonly used, with individual differences influenced by factors such as gender and cultural background. Understanding the coping strategies students employ is critical to developing targeted interventions to support their mental health and well-being.

Coping mechanisms used by students are essential for preventing the harmful effects of academic stress and burnout. Coping strategies, which range from problem-focused to emotion-focused and avoidant coping, are critical in reducing the impact of stressors on students' psychological well-being (Lim et al., 2024). Notably, tolerance of ambiguity appears as an important component impacting learners' coping abilities, particularly in language learning situations (Xu & Ba, 2022). Tolerance of ambiguity reflects an individual's ability to deal with uncertain situations without experiencing undue distress, thereby facilitating adaptive responses to challenging learning contexts.

The observed studies have provided valuable insights into the relationship between academic burnout and coping mechanisms. Lim et al. (2024) discovered a significant beneficial correlation between burnout levels and coping strategies among Filipino college students, suggesting an increased reliance on coping mechanisms as burnout worsened. Similarly, Xu and Ba (2022) emphasized the importance of tolerance for ambiguity while explaining the relationship between stress, burnout, and coping strategies among language learners.

According to Zhou et al. (2023), educational stakeholders are recommended to take proactive measures to enhance students' well-being and academic performance. Implementing stress management training programs and support mechanisms can significantly contribute to reducing academic stress and burnout. Moreover, future studies should explore innovative interventions targeting tolerance of ambiguity to effectively manage academic stress and burnout. By advancing our understanding of coping mechanisms in educational settings, these interventions can lead to more comprehensive and tailored support for students facing academic challenges.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed descriptive design to thoroughly understand the coping mechanisms students use to lessen their academic burnout. Descriptive research design enables researchers to examine and describe how one or more variables are distributed, without considering any causal relationships or other hypotheses. (Aggarwal & Ranganathan, 2019). This study utilized standardized tools such as the Oldenburg Burnout Inventory for Students (OLBI-S) and the Brief-COPE questionnaire to gather data. This enabled us to gain detailed understandings of the different aspects of burnout students face, including exhaustion and disengagement. Additionally, correlation analysis was used to investigate the relationship between academic burnout and various coping strategies. Through this method, the study was able to gather evidence supporting its findings and enhance the understanding of how coping mechanisms may influence or reduce academic burnout (Janse et al., 2021). By using descriptive design, the study not only identified the coping strategies most commonly used by students in response to academic burnout, but also revealed possible methods for intervention and support. By identifying the coping mechanisms that were strongly correlated with reduced levels of academic burnout, this study aims to offer valuable insights into the strategies that may be most effective in reducing academic burnout.

Respondents

A total of three hundred thirty-seven (337) students participated. The sample size was determined using Cochran's (1977) formula. According to a study that utilized Cochran's sample size formula, as cited by Abdullah (2021), it calculates the ideal sample size based on the desired precision level, confidence interval, and the estimated proportion of the attribute in large populations. After calculating

the sample size, a stratified sampling method was employed using students' grade levels and sections as strata, followed by a simple random sampling method. A random number generator software was applied to obtain the study participants from each section in each grade level. This was done to address potential selection and response bias.

Instrument

This study uses two standardized tools to assess students' coping mechanisms for reducing academic burnout. To measure academic burnout, the researchers employed the English version of the Oldenburg Burnout Inventory for Students (OLBI-S), adapted by Reis et al. (2015) from the Oldenburg Burnout Inventory proposed by Demerouti et al. (2005). This instrument exhibits good psychometric properties. Furthermore, the OLBI-S assesses burnout across two dimensions: exhaustion and disengagement, each comprising eight items, with both positively and negatively worded questions. These dimensions closely align with academic burnout, offering a comprehensive evaluation of students' experiences. The scale's Cronbach's alpha value for the tested 16 items was 0.777, indicating good internal consistency (Shrestha et al., 2021).

Coping mechanisms were evaluated using the Brief-COPE, developed as a shorter version of the original 60-item COPE scale (Carver et al., 1989). This 28-item self-report questionnaire measures effective and ineffective coping strategies for dealing with stressful life events, grouped into problem-focused, emotion-focused, and avoidance or dysfunctional coping strategies. According to a study cited by Dagni et al. (2023), the Brief-COPE is a validated instrument with Cronbach's alpha values ranging at 0.83, indicating high reliability.

To ensure the smooth data collection process, the researcher obtained approval from the school principal and consultants. Data collection was done via an online survey administered to randomly selected students in each section and grade level. Each of the randomly selected students was sent a link to Google Forms with the objectives explained, and the written consent form was attached to the form itself. During the data collection phase, real-time monitoring was done to ensure data quality, while measures were implemented to guarantee data security and confidentiality. Upon collection, the gathered data were carefully examined and statistically analyzed to derive insights for the research objectives.

Data Analysis

In conducting this research, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (Spearman's rho) was chosen as the appropriate statistical analysis method for examining the relationship between respondents' levels of academic burnout and their coping mechanisms. This methodological choice was made for several reasons. Firstly, Spearman's rho does not require the data to adhere to the assumption of normal distribution, making it suitable for analyzing ordinal data or data that may not meet the requirements of parametric tests. Given that academic burnout and coping mechanisms are often assessed using Likert-type scales or other ordinal measures, Spearman's rho was deemed well-suited for capturing the relationship between these variables. Additionally, Spearman correlation is preferred as it tends to be relatively robust against outliers, which is particularly relevant when dealing with subjective measures such as burnout and coping (Gupta, 2023). By utilizing Spearman's rho, the study aimed to determine if there is a monotonic relationship between the level of academic burnout and the chosen coping mechanisms, providing valuable insights into how these factors may be related among respondents.

Furthermore, employing a weighted mean as a statistical analysis for describing academic burnout and coping mechanisms offered several benefits. This method allowed for the incorporation of different weights to each response, reflecting their perceived importance or significance. By assigning varying weights to specific data points, the weighted mean analysis accounted for variability in responses, ensuring that outliers or extreme cases were appropriately represented in the analysis (Wallstreetmojo, 2024). Consequently, the weighted mean provided a comprehensive summary of the data, enhancing precision and facilitating a nuanced understanding of the severity and prevalence of burnout symptoms and coping strategies. Overall, the utilization of weighted mean analysis enabled more accurate conclusions and informed decision-making in addressing academic burnout among students.

Following the collection of data from participants' responses, the study proceeded with the analytical phase, employing correlation analysis as the selected methodology. The research aimed to examine the relationship between coping mechanisms and burnout, hypothesizing that there is an existing correlation between the two. Careful consideration was given to the data gathered from Google Forms, ensuring that responses were comprehensively analyzed to provide a clear picture of students' viewpoints on academic burnout. Spearman's rank correlation coefficients were utilized to interpret the degree and direction of the relationship between ranked variables, providing insights into the monotonicity of the relationship. Additionally, weighted mean analysis was employed to interpret average scores assigned to different coping mechanisms, allowing for a deeper exploration of individuals' experiences and the strategies they employ to cope with academic burnout. Overall, the research involved a content analysis of relevant documents to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the results, employing standardized scales or questionnaires to assess coping strategies. This approach facilitated a thorough examination of students' coping mechanisms and their relationship with academic burnout.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analyses and interpretation of data gathered from study participants, categorized into three main sections: academic burnout, coping mechanisms, and the correlation between academic burnout and coping mechanisms. The organization

follows the order of the questions outlined in the statement of the problem.

Academic Burnout of Respondents

Table 1.1 presents the weighted mean distribution and verbal interpretation of coping mechanisms related to academic burnout, focusing on exhaustion.

Table 1.1. *Weighted Mean Distribution and Verbal Interpretation of the Coping Mechanism on Academic Burnout Reduction*

<i>Exhaustion</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
It happens more and more often that I talk about my studies in a negative way.	2.79	Agree
I find my studies to be a positive challenge.	2.69	Agree
Over time, one can become disconnected from this type of study.	2.89	Agree
After a class or after studying, I tend to need more time than in the past in order to relax and feel better.	3.15	Agree
I feel more and more engaged in my studies.	2.72	Agree
After a class or after studying, I usually feel worn out and weary	3.20	Agree
While studying, I often feel emotionally drained.	2.81	Agree
When I study, I usually feel energized.	3.17	Agree
Grand Weighted Mean	2.93	Agree

Legend: 3.26 - 4.00, Strongly Agree; 2.51 - 3.25, Agree; 1.76 - 2.50, Disagree; 1.00 - 1.75, Strongly Disagree

The results indicate that the objectives related to exhaustion are agreed upon by students. All items received a verbal interpretation of "agree," with an overall weighted mean of 2.93, indicating that students tend to agree that they experienced burnout in terms of exhaustion. Additionally, the item "After a class or after studying, I usually feel worn out and weary" received the highest mean of 3.20. Meanwhile, the item "I find my studies to be a positive challenge" received the lowest mean of 2.69, suggesting that students may be experiencing more negative emotions or stress related to their academic activities compared to feeling positively challenged by them.

According to Özhan and Yüksel (2022), exhaustion is often a result of prolonged periods of stress and pressure related to academic demands. The impact of this stress extends beyond minor feelings of fatigue as it can significantly affect students' overall well-being and academic performance.

Moreover, high levels of academic stress can lead to various psychological and physical problems, including depression, anxiety, nervousness, and stress-related disorders (Pacific Teen Treatment, 2021). These issues can further worsen feelings of burnout. Moreover, the negative effects of burnout and stress on mental health can hinder students' ability to concentrate, retain information, and perform well academically.

Table 1.2 continues the analysis, focusing on disengagement. Similar to exhaustion, students generally agree with the statements related to disengagement. All items received a verbal interpretation of "agree," with an overall weighted mean of 2.98, indicating that students tend to agree that they experienced burnout in terms of disengagement. The item "Sometimes I feel sickened by my studies" received the highest mean of 3.22. Feelings of physical and emotional exhaustion, such as being sickened by one's studies, are common indicators of burnout among students (Martínez-Líbano et al., 2021).

Table 1.2. *Weighted Mean Distribution and Verbal Interpretation of the Coping Mechanism on Academic Burnout Reduction*

<i>Disengagement</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I can usually manage my study-related workload well.	2.70	Agree
Sometimes I feel sickened by my studies.	3.22	Agree
I can tolerate the pressure of my studies very well.	2.89	Agree
This is the only field of study that I can imagine myself doing.	2.70	Agree
Lately, I tend to think less about my academic tasks and do them almost mechanically	3.20	Agree
After a class or after studying, I have enough energy for my leisure activities.	3.31	Agree
There are days when I feel tired before I arrive in class or start studying.	2.96	Agree
I always find new and interesting aspects in my studies.	2.83	Agree
General Weighted Mean	2.98	Agree

Legend: 3.26 - 4.00, Strongly Agree; 2.51 - 3.25, Agree; 1.76 - 2.50, Disagree; 1.00 - 1.75, Strongly Disagree

In contrast, the items "I can usually manage my study-related workload well" and "This is the only field of study I can imagine myself doing" received the lowest mean of 2.70. This suggests that although students feel capable of handling their workload and are interested in their field of study, they may still be experiencing some level of dissatisfaction or discomfort with their studies overall. This observation aligns with recent studies on student engagement and satisfaction. The study by Sen (2022) revealed that despite experiencing burnout in certain academic areas, students can still find satisfaction and motivation in others, particularly their interest in their chosen field of study. Additionally, Mamani-Benito et al. (2024) emphasized the intricate relationship between burnout and

academic engagement, underscoring the necessity for customized interventions to address various aspects of student well-being.

Coping Mechanisms of Respondents

Table 2.1 displays the weighted mean distribution and verbal interpretation of coping mechanisms related to academic burnout, focusing on exhaustion. The data shows that students have been engaging in problem-focused coping strategies to a moderate extent. All items received a verbal interpretation of "a little bit," with an overall weighted mean of 3.18, indicating a moderate level of engagement in problem-solving approaches. This suggests students are addressing challenges somewhat, but not extensively.

Table 2.1. *Weighted Mean Distribution and Verbal Interpretation of the Coping Mechanism on Academic Burnout Reduction*

<i>Problem-Focused Coping</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I've been concentrating my efforts on doing something about the situation I'm in.	3.25	A little bit
I've been taking action to try to make the situation better.	3.43	A little bit
I've been getting help and advice from other people.	2.88	A little bit
I've been trying to see it in a different light, to make it seem more positive.	3.17	A little bit
I've been looking for something good in what is happening.	3.22	A little bit
I've been trying to come up with a strategy about what to do.	3.24	A little bit
I've been trying to get advice or help from other people about what to do.	2.94	A little bit
I've been thinking hard about what steps to take.	3.29	A little bit
General Weighted Mean	3.18	A little bit

Legend: 3.26 - 4.00, I've been doing this a lot; 2.51 - 3.25, A little bit; 1.76 - 2.50, A medium amount; 1.00 - 1.75, I haven't been doing this at all

Additionally, the item "I've been taking action to try to make the situation better" received the highest mean of 3.43. This aligns with the study conducted by Freire et al. (2020) where it was found that students often turn to problem-focused coping mechanisms when faced with academic challenges, such as exams or assignments. This approach involves taking concrete steps to address the issue, such as seeking information, making a plan, or taking action. Meanwhile the item "I've been getting help and advice from other people" received the lowest mean of 2.88. This indicates a lesser reliance on external support, possibly suggesting a preference for self-reliance in problem-solving (Aldalaykeh, 2019).

Table 2.2, which focuses on emotion-focused coping, students indicate moderate engagement in various emotion-focused coping strategies. All items received a verbal interpretation of "a little bit," with an overall weighted mean of 3.18, suggesting that respondents generally perceive the level of emotion-focused coping as modest or moderate. This result aligns with the study of Al-Tell and Mansor (2019) where they found that problem focused and emotion-focused coping methods were mostly used by students.

Table 2.2. *Weighted Mean Distribution and Verbal Interpretation of the Coping Mechanism on Academic Burnout Reduction*

<i>Emotion-Focused Coping</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
I've been getting emotional support from others.	2.85	A little bit
I've been saying things to let my unpleasant feelings escape.	2.93	A little bit
I've been criticizing myself.	2.82	A little bit
I've been getting comfort and understanding from someone.	2.88	A little bit
I've been making jokes about it.	3.29	A little bit
I've been accepting the reality of the fact that it has happened.	3.09	A little bit
I've been turning to work or other activities to take my mind off things.	2.99	A little bit
I've been trying to find comfort in my religion or spiritual beliefs.	3.19	A little bit
I've been learning to live with it.	3.13	A little bit
I've been blaming myself for things that happened.	3.15	A little bit
I've been praying or meditating.	2.52	A little bit
I've been making fun of the situation.	2.69	A little bit
General Weighted Mean	2.96	A little bit

Legend: 3.26 - 4.00, I've been doing this a lot; 2.51 - 3.25, A little bit; 1.76 - 2.50, A medium amount; 1.00 - 1.75, I haven't been doing this at all

Additionally, the item 'I've been doing something to think about it less, such as going to movies, watching TV, reading, daydreaming, sleeping, or shopping' received the highest mean of 3.18, while the item 'I've been using alcohol or other drugs to make myself feel better' received the lowest mean of 1.58. A study by Carnahan et al. (2021) aligns with this, indicating that students are more inclined to use distraction and engagement in various activities to cope with difficult situations rather than turning to alcohol or drugs.

Relationship Between the Respondents' Level of Academic Burnout and Their Coping Mechanisms

In table 3, spearman's rho correlation was conducted to determine the relationship between academic burnout and coping mechanisms. The analysis revealed significant correlations between various coping mechanisms and academic burnout. Specifically, a p-value of 0.001, below the 5% significance level we reject the null hypothesis, indicates significant relationships between exhaustion and problem-focused, emotion-focused, and avoidant coping strategies

Table 3. *Correlation between Coping Mechanisms and Academic Burnout*

	Variables	r-value	Relationship	p-value	Sign
Exhaustion	Problem-Focused Coping	.348	weak	<.001	Significant
	Emotion-Focused Coping	.219	weak	<.001	Significant
	Avoidant Coping	.176	weak	0.001	Significant
Disengagement	Problem-Focused Coping	.230	weak	<.001	Significant
	Emotion-Focused Coping	.279	weak	<.001	Significant
	Avoidant Coping	.339	weak	<.001	Significant

The analysis revealed significant correlations between various coping mechanisms and academic burnout. Specifically, a p-value of 0.001, below the 5% significance level we reject the null hypothesis, indicates significant relationships between exhaustion and problem-focused, emotion-focused, and avoidant coping strategies. Additionally, exhaustion and disengagement showed significant correlations with problem-focused, emotion-focused, and avoidant coping. The analysis revealed significant correlations between academic burnout and coping mechanisms, as determined by Spearman's rho coefficients. The relationship between disengagement and exhaustion showed a weak relationship between problem-focused coping, emotion-focused coping, and avoidant coping. Exhaustion demonstrated a moderate positive correlation with problem-focused coping ($r = 0.348$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that as exhaustion levels rise, the employment of problem-focused coping strategies tends to increase. Similarly, exhaustion exhibited weak positive correlations with emotion-focused coping ($r = 0.219$, $p < 0.001$) and avoidant coping ($r = 0.176$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting slight increases in the utilization of these coping mechanisms as exhaustion intensifies. Disengagement also showed weak positive correlations with problem-focused coping ($r = 0.230$, $p < 0.001$), emotion-focused coping ($r = 0.279$, $p < 0.001$), and avoidant coping ($r = 0.339$, $p < 0.001$). The findings strongly suggest that there is a correlation between academic burnout and coping mechanisms. The specific p-values provide some insight, with exhaustion and problem-focused coping having the strongest connection ($p = 0.348$) compared to exhaustion and avoidant coping ($p = 0.176$). This suggests that problem-focused coping might be more prevalent for students experiencing exhaustion.

Proposed Interventions to Address Academic Burnout

The findings of the study emphasize the pressing need to address academic burnout among students, as evidenced by the significant correlations between various coping mechanisms and academic burnout indicators. Specifically, students exhibit high agreement with statements related to exhaustion and disengagement, indicating prevalent experiences of burnout in these areas. Moreover, the moderate engagement in problem-focused and emotion-focused coping strategies suggests a partial but not exhaustive attempt to address academic challenges and emotional distress.

To effectively address academic burnout, treatments should prioritize comprehensive student support. Implementing tutoring and mentorship programs, forming peer support groups, and providing access to academic resources are all important steps toward increasing academic engagement and decreasing feelings of disengagement. Furthermore, measures like the creation of a Mental Health and Well-Being Office in each school division, as required by HB 6574, and the execution of the 2024–2028 Philippine Council for Mental Health (PCMH) Strategic Framework, in partnership with the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Department of Health (DOH), are critical for addressing the more comprehensive mental health requirements of students and advancing well-being in general.

Integrating these interventions into the school environment, along with aligning them with national mental health policies and frameworks, holds the potential to create a supportive ecosystem that empowers students to thrive academically and emotionally. By addressing the prevalence and impact of academic burnout through these concerted efforts, educational institutions can better equip students with the necessary tools and support systems to effectively deal with the challenges of academic life. The Department of Education shall provide sufficient resources for mental health programs and projects designed to maintain and address the mental health and well-being of students. This proposed plan also aims to restore students' activeness when it comes to academics and to maintain students' health.

Conclusions

The research findings offer significant insights into the prevalence of academic burnout among students at Morong National High School, as well as their coping mechanisms and the relationship between these factors. Initially, the analysis highlights the common experience of academic burnout among students, particularly in terms of exhaustion and disengagement. This is evidenced by their agreement with statements reflecting feelings of fatigue, emotional drain, and disinterest in academic tasks.

Subsequently, students employ various coping mechanisms to manage academic stress, including problem-focused, emotion-focused, and avoidant coping strategies. While students exhibit moderate engagement in problem-focused and emotion-focused coping, they tend to employ avoidant coping mechanisms to a lesser extent. This suggests a need for interventions that promote adaptive coping strategies and discourage avoidant behaviors.

Moreover, the correlation analysis reveals significant relationships between academic burnout and coping mechanisms, particularly exhaustion and problem-focused coping, exhaustion and emotion-focused coping, as well as exhaustion and avoidant coping. Similarly, significant correlations exist between disengagement and problem-focused coping, disengagement and emotion-focused coping, and

disengagement and avoidant coping. This implies that students' experiences of exhaustion and disengagement are intricately linked with their adaption of coping strategies, highlighting the significance of addressing both academic burnout and coping mechanisms in educational settings.

Lastly, the proposed action plan outlines several interventions aimed at addressing academic burnout and promoting student well-being. These interventions include implementing stress management programs, providing academic support, and promoting healthy coping mechanisms. By targeting these areas, educators and policymakers can create a supportive environment that enhances students' overall academic performance.

It is recommended, based on the conclusions, that educational institutions prioritize providing resources and support to students experiencing exhaustion and disengagement from academic tasks. This could include counseling services to address stress management and burnout prevention. Additionally, schools should consider organizing sessions to help students develop healthy coping mechanisms, particularly focusing on problem-focused and emotion-focused strategies. The study recommends implementing stress management training programs, enhancing social support networks, and promoting adaptive coping strategies to foster students' well-being and academic success.

For researchers intending to conduct further research on this topic, they must consider exploring the longitudinal effects by conducting studies to assess the long-term effects of different coping mechanisms on academic burnout and overall student well-being. Additionally, examining the roles of faculty and institutional support in influencing student burnout and coping strategies could help identify more effective ways educators and institutions can support students.

References

- Abdulah, D. M. (2021). Prevalence and correlates of COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy in the general public in Iraqi Kurdistan: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Medical Virology*, 93(12), 6722–6731. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmv.27255>
- Addressing the Challenge of Burnout in the Philippines | Mind You. (2022, October 25). Mind You - Mental Health Systems. <https://www.mindyou.com.ph/addressing-the-challenge-of-burnout-in-the-philippines/>
- Alami, N., Elhaddadi, M., Mouden, Z. E., Latifi, M., & Ahami, A. O. T. (2020, September 1). Survey of the prevalence of burnout and depression among high school students. *www.allresearchjournal.com*. <https://www.allresearchjournal.com/archives/?year=2020&vol=6&issue=8&part=E&ArticleId=7035&fbclid=IwAR2nQjVHljMlRpgW7xPGRkPGtSV6b5czOPPGgGI6fmBvZ99b11DcFxpzc4Y>
- Aldalaykeh, M., Al-Hammouri, M. M., & Rababah, J. A. (2019). Predictors of mental health services help-seeking behavior among university students. *Cogent Psychology*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311908.2019.1660520>
- Algorani, E. B., & Gupta, V. (2023, April 24). Coping mechanisms. *StatPearls - NCBI Bookshelf*. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK559031/>
- Al-Tell, M., & Mansor, K. (2019, May 19). Stress Coping Strategies Among Secondary School-Aged Students in Government Schools in Northern West Bank/Palestine. *International Journal of Translational Medical Research and Public Health*. <https://doi.org/10.21106/ijtmrph.78>
- Bill creating DepEd mental health offices for pupils, teachers OK'd on 3rd reading. (2023, January 31). *Manila Bulletin*. <https://mb.com.ph/2023/01/31/bill-creating-deped-mental-health-offices-for-pupils-teachers-okd-on-3rd-reading/>
- Burn-out an “occupational phenomenon”: International Classification of Diseases. (2019, May 28). <https://www.who.int/news/item/28-05-2019-burn-out-an-occupational-phenomenon-international-classification-of-diseases>
- Carnahan, N. D., Carter, M. M., & Sbrocco, T. (2021). Intolerance of Uncertainty, Looming Cognitive Style, and Avoidant Coping as Predictors of Anxiety and Depression During COVID-19: a Longitudinal Study. *International Journal of Cognitive Therapy*, 15(1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41811-021-00123-9>
- Dagani, J., Buizza, C., Ferrari, C., & Ghilardi, A. (2023, June 6). The role of psychological distress, stigma and coping strategies on help-seeking intentions in a sample of Italian College students. *BMC psychology*. https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10243082/?fbclid=IwAR245zPGVanTyHalMii3qQdpGhvV__JFM9qGuPUsHoZZvYjSp_8xd_fu3v4
- Doğan, D. N., & Doğan, D. N. (2023, December 6). SCHOOL BURNOUT IN SECONDARY AND HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Conhecimento & Diversidade*. <https://doi.org/10.18316/rcd.v15i40.11309>
- DOH, WHO launch Philippine Council for Mental Health Strategic Framework 2024-2028. (2023, October 12). *World Health Organization*. <https://www.who.int/philippines/news/detail/12-10-2023-doh--who-launch-philippine-council-for-mental-health-strategic-framework-2024-2028>

- Dung, P. T. T., & Duong, N. T. (2024, April 22). Investigating learning burnout and academic performance among management students: a longitudinal study in English courses. *BioMed Central*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-024-01725-6>
- Freire, C., Del Mar Ferradás, M., Regueiro, B., Martínez, S. R., Arias, A. V., & Núñez, J. C. (2020). Coping Strategies and Self-Efficacy in University Students: A Person-Centered Approach. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00841>
- Gomez, S. L., Sison, C. J., Gavino, M. C., & Tus, J. (2022c). Academic burnout and its relationship on the anxiety of the senior high school students amidst the online learning modality. <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=20279>
- Human Verification. (n.d.). <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Social-Support-And-Academic-Burnout-Among-Secondary-Oyoo/de20f41d58dbc61f8bc176e28570dbf0ad9359bb>
- Kucharzyk, A. A., & Bednarek, A. (2022). Assessment of school stress levels and strategies of coping with stress in high school students. *Pielęgniarstwo XXI Wieku*, 21(4), 218–223. <https://doi.org/10.2478/pielxxiw-2022-0039>
- Lim, J. H., Pacong, J. R. T., Alquizar, C. M. D., & Manaois, J. O. (2024, January 1). Unpacking Post-Pandemic Academic Burnout and Coping Mechanisms among Filipino College Students. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*. <https://doi.org/10.47772/ijriss.2023.7012116>
- Looti, M. (2023, August 28). Oldenburg Burnout Inventory. *PSYCHOLOGICAL SCALES*. <https://scales.arabpsychology.com/s/oldenburg-burnout-inventory/>
- Mamani-Benito, Ó., Esteban, R. F. C., Huayta-Meza, M. V., Castillo-Blanco, R., Chaparro, J. E. T., & García, W. G. (2024). Emotional fatigue, academic engagement, and satisfaction with studies during the return to post-pandemic university attendance. *Frontiers in Education*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2024.1297302>
- Marôco, J., Assunção, H., Harju-Luukkainen, H., Lin, S. W., Sit, P., Cheung, K., Maloa, B. F. S., Ilić, I. S., Smith, T. J., & Cam (PDF) affective structures among students and its ... (n.d.). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/322232990_Affective_Structures_among_Students_and_its_Relationship_with_Academic_Burnout_with_Emphasis_on_Gender
- Martínez-Líbano, J., Yeomans, M. M., Campusano, N. G., & Flores, E. C. (2021). Emotional exhaustion and mental health in a sample of Chilean social science students during the COVID-19 pandemic. <https://www.redalyc.org/journal/6723/672371742002/html/>
- Mental health in basic education bill hurdles House 2nd reading. (n.d.). Philippine News Agency. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1193479#:~:text=Under%20HB%206574%2C%20a%20Mental,and%20personnel%20of%20the%20DepEd.>
- Özhan, M. B., & Yüksel, G. (2022). The Effect of School Burnout on Academic Achievement and Well-Being in High School Students: A Holistic Model Proposal. *International Journal of Contemporary Educational Research*, 8(1), 145–162. <https://doi.org/10.33200/ijcer.824488>
- Reis, D., Xanthopoulou, D., & Tsaousis, I. (2015). Measuring job and academic burnout with the Oldenburg Burnout Inventory (OLBI): Factorial invariance across samples and countries. *Burnout Research*, 2(1), 8–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.burn.2014.11.001>
- Republic Act No. 11036. (n.d.). https://lawphil.net/statutes/repacts/ra2018/ra_11036_2018.html
- Sağar, M. E. (2022). Predictors of Subjective Well-Being at School in Adolescents: emotion regulation, coping and Cognitive Flexibility. *Ege Eğitim Dergisi*, 23(2), 133–149. <https://doi.org/10.12984/egteed.1060883>
- Sen, E. O. (n.d.). Middle school students' engagement in mathematics and learning approaches: structural equation modelling. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1337280>
- Shrestha, D. B., Katuwal, N., Tamang, A., Paudel, A., Gautam, A., Sharma, M., Bhusal, U., & Budhathoki, P. (2021, June 24). Burnout among medical students of a medical college in Kathmandu; A cross-sectional study. *PloS One*. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0253808>
- Jain, A. (2024, March 15). Weighted Mean Formula. *WallStreetMojo*. <https://www.wallstreetmojo.com/weighted-mean-formula/>
- Wang, S., Li, H., Chen, X., Yan, N., & Wen, D. (2022, December 13). Learning burnout and its association with perceived stress, social support, and the Big Five personality traits in Chinese medical students during the COVID-19 pandemic: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Psychiatry*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-022-04453-6>
- Xu, J., & Ba, Y. (2022). Coping with students' stress and burnout: Learners' ambiguity of tolerance. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 842113. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.842113>
- Zhou, X., Bambling, M., Bai, X., & Edirippulige, S. (2023, March 31). Chinese school adolescents' stress experience and coping strategies: a qualitative study. *BMC Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-023-01137-y>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Leighna Blessy T. Robles

Morong National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Emerald Jane F. Ramos

Morong National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Ellyza Joy F. Balmes

Morong National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Jillian Justine R. Feniquito

Morong National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Mark Leander V. Cheungkock

Morong National High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Kathleen D. U. San Juan

Morong National High School
Department of Education – Philippines